

The seventh international scientific
and professional conference

“THE RIGHT TO ACCESS (MENTAL) HEALTH CARE”

Book of Abstracts

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ACADEMIC STRESS OF UNIVERSITY STUDENTS WITH DISABILITIES

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Abstract: Students with disabilities may be exposed to additional academic stress due to inadequate adjustment of the physical and social environment. The goal of the research was to determine whether students with disabilities in the territory of the Republic of Serbia are exposed to a higher level of academic stress compared to students without disabilities. 236 students participated in the research, of which 26 declared themselves as students with disabilities. In order to collect data, The Perception of Academic Stress (PAS) Scale was used. Students with disabilities reported higher levels of academic stress than students without disabilities in the domains of stress related to academic expectations, stress related to assignments and exams, and on the total score of the questionnaire. Regarding students with

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disabilities, a statistically significant correlation was obtained between the age of the respondents and the level of stress due to assignments and exams at the university, while gender, level of study, average grade during studies and use of support measures were not statistically significantly related to individual domains or the overall academic stress.

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